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STEERING THE CUSTOMER TRAJECTORY TOWARDS E-RETAILING – A CASE STUDY OF NETIZENS AT BELLARY

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Abstract

Problem Statement: Traditional retailing is being outrun by the organized retail sector, which in recent times has been overshadowed by one of the fast growing mode of retailing – ‘e-Retailing’. The usage of internet has increased phenomenally, due to convenience and wide assortments, customers willing to make online purchases are ever escalating; inspite of the aforesaid developments still bulk of customers from tier-II cities are refraining from making online purchases. Even if they make purchase online, they are limiting it to only few product categories, of low economic value. It is important for online retailers to break this shackle to leap ahead. Thus an empirical study has been initiated to understand the various factors restraining the customers towards e-retailing and suggest suitable marketing strategies to overcome the tide.

Keywords: organized retailing, e-retailing, assortment, economic value

Introduction

Online retailing is a system of electronic commerce which enables consumers to purchase goods and services from distant sellers over the World Wide Web. Mobile commerce (or [m-commerce](#)) describes purchasing from an online retailer's mobile optimized online site or app. Gone are those days of brick and mortar shops, nowadays consumers prefer convenience in shopping, which the major USP instrumental in popularizing the e-retailing. This upsurge is evident as more and more companies are offering online interfaces for consumers. Now companies are having the option of reaching the distant located consumers, and unlimited possibilities of expanding the market and customer base.

E-retailing idea was initially conceived by English entrepreneur Mr. Michael Aldrich in the year 1979, which changed the way we shop today. He transformed and connected the modified domestic television set into a virtual transaction processing system using telephone connectivity. He named it as Videotex, the modified domestic TV technology with a simple menu-driven human-computer interface, was a 'new, universally applicable, participative communication medium — the first since the invention of the telephone.' E-retailing provides consumers product of interest, ability to compare with alternative vendors using a shopping search engine. Once the product is selected by the consumer, the online retailers use shopping cart software to allow the consumer to accumulate multiple items and to adjust quantities, like filling a physical shopping cart or basket in a conventional store. A "checkout" process follows (continuing the physical-store analogy) in which payment and delivery information is collected, if necessary Some stores allow consumers to sign up for a permanent online account so that some or all of this information only needs to be entered once. The consumer often receives an e-mail confirmation once the transaction is complete. Merely sophisticated online retailers look for the mail orders or telephone orders from the consumers to dispatch the goods. There are different payment choices available for consumers, but popular are credit card/debit card payments and cash on delivery.

Course: The research problem is stated at point section-1; significance of the study is revealed at section-2; the objectives of the study are discussed at section-3; the methodology adopted by the researchers is depicted at section-4; data analysis is discussed at section-5; findings & conclusion from the study is stated at section-6; suggested strategic marketing imperatives are depicted at section-7.

Section-1 Statement of the Problem: Retailing scenario is transforming from brick & mortar base to virtual space; the e-retailing is accepted well among the metro cities, but not so profusely accepted among tier-II cities. It is need of the hour for e-retailing companies to overcome this refusal; thus a study has been conducted to assess the Netigens response at Bellary city towards the e-retailing.

Section-2 Significance of the Study

The study connotes the significant role of marketing in understanding and eradicating the refraining factors which are influencing consumers to stay away or limit their purchases online, and increase the e-retailing traffic and expand it to wide product categories.

Section-3 Objectives of the study:

1. To understand the preparedness of the consumers in coming forward to shop online.
2. To ascertain factors restraining people from e-retailing.
3. To suggest imperatives for limiting the influence of restraining factors on consumer's e-retailing preference.
4. To suggest suitable marketing strategies for increasing the e-retailing traffic.

Section-4 Methodology

Bellary, a tier-II city from Karnataka has been chosen for the purpose of the study. Random sampling procedure was followed to select sample respondents from the sampling area, looking into convenience 40 respondents were selected. The basic research design is based on primary source of data; however, secondary sources are also taken into consideration. Data were collected from the above respondents, using interview schedule specifically designed for the purpose; Tabulated data was analyzed with the help of statistical techniques such as, Correlation coefficients, Mean, Variance, Standard Deviation, Factor analysis and simple percentages, to know the extent of identified factors in influencing the people's restraining behavior with respect to e-retailing.

Section-5 Data Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 1 hour	21	52.5	52.5	52.5
	1 - 2 hours	13	32.5	32.5	85.0
	3 - 4 hours	3	7.5	7.5	92.5
	more than 4 hours	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	< one year	3	7.5	7.5	7.5
	1 - 2 years	4	10.0	10.0	17.5
	2 - 3 years	13	32.5	32.5	50.0
	> 3 years	20	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Novice	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
	Intermediate	15	37.5	37.5	55.0
	Advanced	18	45.0	45.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

S.No	Usage of Internet	Never	Occasionally	Frequently	Every time	Mean	S.D	Variance
1	News	32.5	45	17.5	5	1.95	0.846	0.715
2	Gaming	15	15	20	50	3.05	1.131	1.279
3	Chatting		10	32.5	57.5	3.48	0.679	0.461
4	Education		10	27.5	62.5	3.52	0.679	0.461
5	Product information	2.5	12.5	27.5	57.5	3.40	0.810	0.656
6	Shopping	7.5	17.5	55	20	2.88	0.822	0.676
7	Surfing		10	37.5	52.5	3.42	0.675	0.456
8	Communication		7.5	27.5	65	3.58	0.636	0.404
9	Work/business		12.5	30	57.5	3.45	0.714	0.510

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	< Rs.500	1	2.5	2.5	2.5
	Rs.500 - 1000	6	15.0	15.0	17.5
	Rs.1000 - 2000	2	5.0	5.0	22.5
	Rs.2000 - 3000	5	12.5	12.5	35.0
	Rs.3000 - 5000	12	30.0	30.0	65.0
	Rs.5000 - 10000	10	25.0	25.0	90.0
	> Rs.10000	4	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Customer Opinion	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Indifferent	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean	S.D	Variance
Online Saves Time	-	5.00%	12.50%	35.00%	47.50%	100.00%	4.25	0.87	0.756

Online Great Advantage	-	5.00%	10.00%	30.00%	55.00%	100.00%	4.35	0.864	0.746
More Difficult to shop	-	40.00%	50.00%	10.00%	-	100.00%	2.7	0.648	0.421
Prefer Conventional Shopping	-	15.00%	57.50%	27.50%	-	100.00%	3.12	0.648	0.42
Prefer Online if Prices are Low	-	10.00%	10.00%	55.00%	25.00%	100.00%	3.95	0.876	0.767
Deliveries are Delayed	-	7.50%	10.00%	60.00%	22.50%	100.00%	3.98	0.8	0.64
Wide Assortment in Online	-	15.00%	25.00%	60.00%	-	100.00%	4.45	0.749	0.562
Description is Accurate	-	32.50%	52.50%	15.00%	-	100.00%	2.82	0.675	0.456
Information is Sufficient	-	20.00%	15.00%	57.50%	7.50%	100.00%	3.52	0.905	0.82
Online is Secured	5.00%	20.00%	52.50%	15.00%	7.50%	100.00%	3	0.934	0.872
Hesitation to Give Cr. Card No.	-	10.00%	10.00%	25.00%	55.00%	100.00%	4.25	1.006	1.013
Online reduces monetary cost	-	7.50%	12.50%	25.00%	55.00%	100.00%	4.28	0.96	0.922
Asking Cr. Card No. is Lacuna	-	-	15.00%	40.00%	45.00%	100.00%	4.3	0.723	0.523
Dissatisfied with product performance	-	12.50%	12.50%	52.50%	22.50%	100.00%	3.85	0.921	0.849

Correlation Coefficient The correlation coefficient between a variable and itself is always 1, hence the principal diagonal of the correlation matrix contains 1^s. The correlation coefficients above and below the principal diagonal are the same. The determinant of the correlation matrix is shown at the foot of the table below (table – 7)

Table 7: Correlation Martix

	Online Saves Time	Online Great Advantage	More Difficult To Shop	I Prefer Conventional Shopping	Prefer Online If Prices Are Low	Delivery Is Delayed	Wide Assortment Online	Description Online Is Accurate	Information Is Sufficient	Online Is Secured	Hesitate To Give Credit Card No	Reduced Monetary Costs Online	Credit Card Request Lacuna	Dissatisfied With Product Perf
Online Saves Time	1.000	-.119	.136	.080	-.152	-.028	.216	.033	-.138	.221	-.103	.038	-.041	-.016
Online Great Advantage	-.119	1.000	-.082	-.080	.566	.236	-.368	-.112	.316	-.064	.133	-.119	-.337	.261
More Difficult To Shop	.136	-.082	1.000	-.092	-.343	-.212	-.084	-.064	-.074	-.169	-.039	-.070	-.077	-.249
I Prefer Conventional Shopping	.080	-.080	-.092	1.000	.282	.155	.409	.110	.147	.339	-.128	-.098	.191	.032
Prefer Online If Prices Are Low	-.152	.566	-.343	.282	1.000	.364	-.199	.072	.325	.094	-.102	-.166	-.178	.086

Delivery Is Delayed	-.028	.236	-.212	.155	.364	1.000	.019	-.151	.125	-.137	.135	-.191	-.075	.064
Wide Assortment Online	.216	-.368	-.084	.409	-.199	.019	1.000	-.246	-.055	.330	.017	.180	.407	-.011
Description Online Is Accurate	.033	-.112	-.064	.110	.072	-.151	-.246	1.000	-.181	.041	-.311	.076	-.047	-.126
Information Is Sufficient	-.138	.316	-.074	.147	.325	.125	-.055	-.181	1.000	-.152	-.063	-.200	-.090	.066
Online Is Secured	.221	-.064	-.169	.339	.094	-.137	.330	.041	-.152	1.000	-.055	-.029	.076	.238
Hesitate To Give Credit Card No	-.103	.133	-.039	-.128	-.102	.135	.017	-.311	-.063	-.055	1.000	.272	.141	.152
Reduced Monetary Costs Online	.038	-.119	-.070	-.098	-.166	-.191	.180	.076	-.200	-.029	.272	1.000	.358	-.039
Credit Card No Requirement Is Lacuna	-.041	-.337	-.077	.191	-.178	-.075	.407	-.047	-.090	.076	.141	.358	1.000	-.162
Dissatisfied With Product Performance	-.016	.261	-.249	.032	.086	.064	-.011	-.126	.066	.238	.152	-.039	-.162	1.000

Table 8: Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Online Saves Time	1.000	.433
Online Great Advantage	1.000	.660
More Difficult To Shop	1.000	.582
I Prefer Conventional Shopping	1.000	.693
Prefer Online If Prices Are Low	1.000	.763
Delivery Is Delayed	1.000	.417
Wide Assortment Online	1.000	.783
Description Online Is Accurate	1.000	.775
Information Is Sufficient	1.000	.484
Online Is Secured	1.000	.705
Hesitate To Give Credit Card No	1.000	.658
Reduced Monetary Costs Online	1.000	.612
Credit Card No. Req Is Lacuna	1.000	.694
Dissatisfied With Product Perf	1.000	.645
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Communalities

The next item from the output is a table of communalities (Table-8) which shows how much of the variance in the variables has been accounted for by the extracted factors. I.e. over 78.3% of the variance in ‘wide assortment online’ is accounted for; while 41.7% of the variance in ‘delivery is delayed’.

Total Variance Explained

The next item (table-9) shows all the factors extractable from the analysis along with their Eigen values, the percent of variance attributable to each factor, and the cumulative variance of the factor and the previous factors. Notice that the first factor accounts for 18.677% of the variance, the second 14.534% third 11.867%, fourth factor 9.318%, and the fifth factor 9.220%. All the remaining factors are not significant.

Table 9: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.613	18.667	18.667	2.613	18.667	18.667	2.277	16.261	16.261
2	2.035	14.534	33.202	2.035	14.534	33.202	2.074	14.814	31.075
3	1.661	11.867	45.069	1.661	11.867	45.069	1.520	10.859	41.934
4	1.304	9.318	54.386	1.304	9.318	54.386	1.517	10.838	52.772
5	1.291	9.220	63.606	1.291	9.220	63.606	1.517	10.834	63.606
6	.960	6.855	70.461						
7	.888	6.342	76.803						
8	.742	5.299	82.102						
9	.631	4.504	86.606						
10	.509	3.634	90.240						
11	.479	3.420	93.660						
12	.359	2.564	96.224						
13	.304	2.169	98.393						
14	.225	1.607	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Scree Plot: The scree plot is a graph of the eigenvalues against all the factors. The graph is useful for determining how many factors to retain. The point of interest is where the curve starts to flatten. It can be seen that the curve begins to flatten between factors 4 and 5. Note also that factor after 5 has an eigenvalue of less than 1, so only five factors have been retained

Table 10: Component Matrix^a

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Online Saves Time					
Online Great Advantage	.777				
More Difficult To Shop					
I Prefer Conventional Shopping		.733			
Prefer Online If Prices Are Low	.725				
Delivery Is Delayed					
Wide Assortment Online	-.525	.638			
Description Online Is Accurate			-.598		-.590
Information Is Sufficient	.506				

Component (Factor) Matrix
The (table-10) shows the loadings of the 14 variables on the five factors extracted. The higher the absolute value of the loading, the more the factor contributes to the variable. The gap on the table represent loadings that are less than 0.5, this makes reading the table easier. We suppressed all loadings less than 0.5.

Online Is Secured		.615			
Hesitate To Give Credit Card No.			.796		
Reduced Monetary Costs Online					
Credit Card No. Requirement Is Lacuna	-.540				
Dissatisfied With Product Performance				.610	
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a. 5 components extracted.					

Table 11: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Online Saves Time					
Online Great Advantage	.573				
More Difficult To Shop					
I Prefer Conventional Shopping		.718			
Prefer Online If Prices Are Low	.792				
Delivery Is Delayed	.606				
Wide Assortment Online		.832			
Description Online Is Accurate				-.855	
Information Is Sufficient	.623				
Online Is Secured					.645
Hesitate To Give Credit Card No.				.624	
Reduced Monetary Costs Online			.723		
Credit Card No. Requirement Is Lacuna		.521	.581		
Dissatisfied With Product Performance					.763
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. a. rotation converged in 11 iterations.					

Rotated Component (Factor) Matrix

(Table-11) The idea of rotation is to reduce the number factors on which the variables under investigation have high loadings. 'online is secured', 'dissatisfied with product performance' are substantially loaded on factor (component) 5, 'description online is accurate' 'hesitate to give credit card number', are substantially loaded on Factor (Component) 4; 'reduced monetary costs online' 'credit card No. requirement is a lacuna', are substantially loaded on Factor (Component) 3, 'I prefer conventional shopping' 'wide assortment online' and 'credit card number requirement is a lacuna' are substantially loaded on Factor (Component) 2; while 'All the remaining variables are substantially loaded on Factor 1. These factors can be used as variables for further analysis.

Table 12: Distribution of Factors Influencing Internet Purchases

Items	Very Imp	Un-Imp	Neutral	Imp	Very Imp	Mean	S.D	Var
Delivery time	--	--	10.00%	20.00%	70.00%	4.6	0.672	0.451
Reputation of Co.	--	--	10.00%	30.00%	60.00%	4.5	0.679	0.462
Guarantees	--	--	2.50%	15.00%	82.50%	4.8	0.464	0.215
Privacy Of Info	10.00%	--	15.00%	10.00%	65.00%	4.3	1.067	1.138
Good Description	--	--	17.50%	15.00%	67.50%	4.5	0.784	0.615
Security	--	--	15.00%	15.00%	70.00%	4.55	0.749	0.562
Prices	--	--	17.50%	15.00%	67.50%	4.5	0.784	0.615

Items	Very Un-Imp	Un-Imp	Neutral	Imp	Very Imp	Mean	S.D	Var
Waiting time	5.00%	5.00%	15.00%	45.00%	30.00%	3.9	1.057	1.118
Risk of credit	-	-	12.50%	25.00%	62.50%	4.5	0.716	0.513
Identity theft	10.00%	-	7.50%	35.00%	47.50%	4.2	0.966	0.933
Difficult to return		-	12.50%	37.50%	50.00%	4.38	0.705	0.497
Risk of getting unordered	12.50%	-	20.00%	55.00%	12.50%	3.68	0.859	0.738
Loss of privacy	17.50%	-	10.00%	25.00%	47.50%	4.02	1.143	1.307
Not skillful with internet	-	-	7.50%	72.50%	20.00%	4.12	0.516	0.266
Lack of trust	17.50%	-	15.00%	32.50%	35.00%	3.85	1.099	1.208
Complex activity	10.00%	17.50%	5.00%	27.50%	40.00%	3.7	1.418	2.01
Lack of tangibility	7.50%	-	7.50%	35.00%	50.00%	4.28	0.905	0.82
Expensive over retail	10.00%	17.5	12.50%	12.50%	47.50%	3.7	1.471	2.164
Bad experience	10.00%	-	5.00%	17.50%	67.50%	4.42	0.984	0.969

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Diploma	4	10.0	10.0	10.0
	Graduate	19	47.5	47.5	57.5
	Post Graduate	12	30.0	30.0	87.5
	Doctorate	5	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Self Employed	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
	Salaried	15	37.5	37.5	52.5
	Professional	11	27.5	27.5	80.0
	Student	8	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	< 2 Lakhs	2	5.0	5.0	5.0
	2 - 3 Lakhs	18	45.0	45.0	50.0
	3 - 5 Lakhs	15	37.5	37.5	87.5
	5 - 8 Lakhs	5	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Section-6 Findings & Conclusion:

- About 52.5% of the respondents use internet for less than one hour;
- 50% of the respondents are using the internet since 1 – 3 years;
- 17.5% of the respondents expressed themselves as novices w.r.t internet usage; where as 37.5% respondents expressed they have intermediate internet knowledge and 45% expressed that they are advanced in internet usage.

- About 7.5% people never used internet for shopping; 17.5% people use internet for shopping occasionally;
- About 35% of the respondents spend between Rs.500 to Rs.3000 per transaction on internet shopping.
- 82.5% of the respondents expressed that deliveries are often delayed in e-retailing;
- 52% respondents were indifferent w.r.t to description accuracy of the products on e-retailing; 25% respondents disagreed and 52.5% respondents were indifferent w.r.t. security of transactions on e-retailing;
- 70% of the respondents were hesitating to give their credit card details while shopping on e-retailing;
- 74.5% respondents were dissatisfied with the performance of the products purchased online.
- In communalities table (table 8) Over 78.3% of the variance is noticed in 'wide assortment online'; while 41.7% of the variance in 'delivery is delayed'. Notice that the first factor accounts for 18.677% of the variance, the second 14.534% third 11.867%, fourth factor 9.318%, and the fifth factor 9.220%. All the remaining factors are not significant.
- 82.5% respondents felt identity theft is important factor restraining them from e-retailing.
- Other factors restraining are: waiting time, risk of credit, difficult to return, risk of getting un-ordered, lack of privacy, lack of skill in internet usage, lack of tangibility, complex activity, bad past experiences etc influenced the restraining behaviour of the Netizens at Bellary towards shopping through e-retailing.

Section-7 Strategic Marketing Imperatives

In order to increase the customer traffic the e-retailing companies has to adopt the following marketing imperatives:

- Increase the media presence,
- Maximize search engine visibility,
- Create remarkable content,
- Leverage social media – interact with customers and prospects.
- Extend reach with advertising – create branded banners and start Google display network campaign.
- Identify target websites for campaigns.
- Engage affiliate networks,
- Hire inbound marketer.
- Design simple, unambiguous and user friendly website.
- Design proactive logistics system, which ensures timely delivery to keep the promises made to customers.
- Ensure the security of the transactions with advanced hacker proof soft wares, firewalls and malware protectors.
- Protect the customer's confidential identities such as bank account number, credit card number from being placed in wrong hands.
- Ensure the displayed products and actual products are of similar identical quality.
- Instead of loyalty programs (which may not lead to effective ROI) go for using the same funds for other value adding offerings to customers like- free shipping, easy replacement, EMI etc.

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